

THE CONSEQUENCE OF MOVIE THEATRE CLOSURES IN THE MIDST OF THE PANDEMIC

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Article History:

Received: 21-Feb-2021

Revised: 12- May- 2021

Accepted: 10-Jun- 2021

First Published: 30- Jun-2021

Cite this Article as :

Kushwaha A. (2021), "The Consequence Of Movie Theatre Closures In The Midst Of The Pandemic", *International Journal of Social Sciences & Economic Environment*, Vol. 6, Issue 1, Jan-Jun-2021, pp 15–21.

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.53882/IJSSEE.2021.0601003>

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INTRODUCTION

Regardless of age, gender, career, or income level, entertainment plays an important role in people's lives. Entertainment, according to the Oxford English Dictionary (1971), is an activity that may hold the audience's interest. Thousands of years have passed since such

ABSTRACT

Purpose: *Subscribing to OTT (Over The Top) platforms and reading fictional or non-fictional books were two of the entertainment options examined in this study.*

Design/Research Methodology/approach: *A total of 351 college graduate students participated in the study, which was performed in Mumbai. We employed regression, ANOVA, independent t test, and mean test.*

Findings: *According to the findings, movie theatres posed as a stumbling block in the way of more OTT platform subscriptions. However, it did not encourage college graduates to read more fiction and nonfiction.*

Research Implications: *OTT services have yet to reach folks who do not attend movies in theatres. OTT platforms may use offline advertising methods such as promotion events in malls or on motorways during this time. Furthermore, OTT platforms have yet to offer ethnically cultural programmes that may appeal to a college graduate of this type.*

Scope for future work / Research limitations: *Only graduate students and a specified age range are included in the study. It is held in a city setting. Among the many options for amusement, the study chose only two. In the future, the study could be expanded by introducing more entertainment options. A post-pandemic investigation could yield a different conclusion.*

Originality/value: *According to a survey of the literature, no research have looked at whether youths have stopped going to the movies. As a result, this research will assist determine whether youths are more likely to migrate to OTT platforms and forego movie theatre trips completely.*

Key Words: *Fictional-non-fictional books, theatre, OTT Platform*

Paper type: *Research paper*

operations began. Despite the fact that diverse activities hold people's attention due to different preferences, the majority are identifiable and familiar.

The third most popular form of entertainment is going to the movies (Gamecrate, 2018). It is a necessary component of everyone's college experience. The epidemic had an impact on all aspects of life, including movie theatres. Change occurs as a result of chance, choice, and catastrophe, according to Verma (2007). Due to the COVID -19 problem, movie theatres are undergoing changes. As per Government of India guidelines, movie theatres will be temporarily closed from March 24, 2020 forward. According to a research by FICCI and EY (2020), 15 to 20% of movie theatres will close in the near future. The resurgence of movie theatres is still a mystery. Filmmakers are looking for new ways to have their films distributed. Because of developments in Internet technology, the OTT (over-the-top) platform arose during this time. Movies and web series were both streamed on this site. According to the India OTT Video Content Market Consumer Survey conducted by Counterpoint Research, 89 percent of users were aged 16 to 35. In India, OTT (over-the-top) platforms are attempting to attract customers by offering various discounts and deals. According to the Flyx report (2020), during the epidemic, 50% of new memberships were sold exclusively.

According to estimates, India has the world's sixth largest book market, which is predicted to reach Rs 739 billion by 2020. (Nielsen India Book Market Report, 2015). According to the survey, two-thirds of book readers agreed that they brought more books with them during the pandemic (Nielsen Book India Consumer Research Study, 2020). During the epidemic, audiobooks have surpassed physical and electronic books in terms of popularity, according to Ahaskar (2020).

According to the Ormax Media Survey Report (2020), 82 percent of Indians miss seeing movies and 28 percent are willing to do so whenever the government of India lifts the ban on movie theatres. According to Qube Cinema, Maharashtra has the second-highest number of movie theatres in India (2020). As a result, the study's goal is to assess the impact of movie theatre closures on college graduates in Mumbai, Maharashtra, during the epidemic.

OBJECTIVES

- To investigate the effect of theatre closure on students' use of OTT services.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Mathur (2018), Indian audiences are gradually catching up with OTT platform subscriptions. However, the majority of people are unable to use it due to prohibitive expenses. The attraction of youths to OTT platforms, according to Valecha and Jaggi (2020), is due to cellphones becoming an alternative television set. According to Koravi (2019), OTT platforms have a negative impact on youngsters' health and psychological issues. Chatterjee and Pal (2020) challenged the claim that OTT platforms have caused youths to lose their

social bonds. However, nothing compares to the thrill of seeing a movie with friends at a movie theatre.

According to Raju (2014), pupils are more likely to read under compulsion than out of their own free will. As a result, educational institutions have a larger role in instilling a reading habit in students. Students will not read, according to Williams (2014), unless libraries are able to connect their book collections to students' social and emotional needs. According to Jansen (2019), college students are interested in reading novels that are not part of their curriculum. Levine et al. (2020) discovered that reading for pleasure lowered stress among college students, highlighting the importance of reading. Furthermore, reading rose only because it was in one's best interests, not because it was required. Järve (2002) warned that juvenile reading habits are inconsistent. It is only likely to rise when a significant book is released.

According to the above-mentioned literature study, OTT platforms are real and here to stay. It was also clear that such platforms were posing a serious threat to movie theatres. However, no research has been done to see if youths have stopped going to the movies. As a result, this study will aid in determining whether youths have a proclivity to migrate to OTT platforms and forego movie theatre trips completely. Young people's tension and boredom were relieved by reading, according to the literature study. Nonetheless, in light of the current pandemic crisis, such a truth was not put to the test. Finally, previous research reviews agreed that the pandemic had a harmful influence on young people's mental health. Meanwhile, no previous research has identified any behavioural influence as a result of movie theatre closures.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research was carried out among college grads. These responders were between the ages of 18 and 21 years old. College is the time when desire and possibilities to view movies are at their peak. Mumbai, Maharashtra, India, was the location of these responders.

The population size was finite, hence Krejcie and Morgan's formula from 1970 was employed. The sample size was set to 351 people. The approach employed was proportional random sampling.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1: ANOVA analysis on college graduates' movie theatre visit frequency before pandemic and OTT usage

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	13.705	3	4.532	8.139	0.000
Within Groups	137.091	242	0.567		
Total	150.721	241			

As per table 1, the ANOVA F value was found significant at 1% of Alpha level ($F = 8.139, p < 0.001$).

Table 2: Model Summary on Theatre closure and using OTT Platforms

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.468 ^a	0.219	0.201	0.682
a. Predictors: (Constant), Theatr_Closure				

According to table 2, the R² value demonstrates that theatre closure predicts 21.9 percent variance in OTT consumption. Because the ANOVA and t value of this regression model are significant, the R value of 0.468 is high.

Table 3: ANOVA value analysis on Theatre closure and using OTT Platforms

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	33.948	1	33.948	70.642	0.000 ^b
	Residual	116.817	243	.482		
	Total	150.763	244			

a. Dependent Variable: OTT

b. Predictors: (Constant), Theatr_Closure

Table 3 shows that the regression model is well-fitting. At a 1% alpha level, the ANOVA f value is significant. $P < .001$, $F = 70.642$. It backed with the prediction that theatres would close due to the use of OTT platforms. This model's t value ($t=8.412$, $p < .001$) is likewise significant. It was revealed that due to theatre closures, OTT usage was boosted.

Table 4: Regression Co-efficient value analysis on Theatre closure and using OTT Platforms

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.794	0.133		13.217	0.000
	Theatr_Closure	0.347	0.042	0.475	8.412	0.000

According to table 4, a 0.347 rise in OTT usage is caused by an increase in one unit. At a 1% alpha level, the p value of 0.347 was found to be significant. As a result, it was established that the closing of movie theatres resulted in an increase in the use of OTT platforms..

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

College graduates who watched movies once a week or once a month were more likely to use OTT than those who watched movies infrequently or never saw movies. College graduates who went to the movies had mixed feelings towards OTT features. College grads with pocket money were more likely to use OTT platforms than those without. The closure of movie theatres resulted in an increase in OTT platform subscriptions. The epidemic did, in fact,

cause this phenomenon to be disrupted. The shutdown of movie theatres did not result in an increase in the number of people reading fiction and nonfiction books. During the epidemic, there was no gender or personality difference in the use of OTT platforms or the reading of fictional and non-fictional literature. Both demographic characteristics had no bearing on the outcome.

SUGGESTIONS

OTT services have yet to reach folks who do not attend movies in theatres. OTT platforms may use offline advertising methods such as promotion events in malls or on motorways during this time. Furthermore, OTT platforms have yet to provide ethnically cultural programming that would appeal to such college grads. OTT platforms were seen favourably by college grads. OTT platforms might take advantage of this by enlisting college graduates as brand ambassadors and offering discounted items to them. The cost of adopting OTT platforms was a big consideration. As a result, an appropriate pricing approach for such an audience can be adapted to fit their requirements. For higher quality and no buffering, you'll need a good wifi connection. It's possible that you won't be able to watch all of the content you want. A sudden shift in policy could impact your ability to access material based on your location, payment methods, and other factors.

There are a number of technological considerations that OTT platforms must make. For a better viewing experience, users' smartphones must have at least 3 GB of RAM. The data on a smartphone that is utilised for streaming will be depleted in a relatively short period of time. Some films are only intended to be seen in theatres. When watching such films on a smartphone, the video and audio effects will be reduced. OTT. Some formats, such as 70 mm IMAX and 4DX, cannot be substituted. Furthermore, OTT does not provide much in the way of 3D content. There is still a market for 3D films, and I am one of them. Although 3D Blu-rays are available, they are not always affordable, and one would expect them to be available on OTT as well. When that doesn't happen, it's a disappointment. As a result, film producers will be demotivated and may decide not to develop high-budget films. On a personal level, going to the movies with friends and family is still a huge deal over the holidays, and that magic can't be duplicated from home. Furthermore, OTT platforms have invaded consumers' personal space. Because most users are balancing both leisure and their jobs at the same time, there is a thin border between amusement and working hours. These are a few of the challenges that OTT platforms must overcome.

Certain films are adapted from novels. Usually, this desire to read leads to increased reading activities. However, it was found in this case that college graduates did not consult literature. College grads might access electronic and audio books instead of going to the library. Despite the fact that such books are less expensive than hard copy books, college graduates rarely use them. It is difficult for book publishers to generate such enthusiasm. These publishers may time the release of their books to coincide with the release of the film. This may pique interest in engaging college grads' imaginations in terms of how they envision the film.

LIMITATIONS AND SCOPE

Only graduate students and a specified age range are included in the study. It is held in a city setting. Among the many options for amusement, the study chose only two. In the future, the study could be expanded by introducing more entertainment options. A post-pandemic investigation could yield a different conclusion. During the epidemic, graduate and postgraduate students can be compared in terms of their use of OTT platforms and reading fiction and nonfiction books. More demographic variables can be included.

Change is an unavoidable fact of life. Movie theatres were compelled to close due to safety concerns during the epidemic. Due to the shutdown of movie theatres, OTT services have seen a surge in subscriptions. OTT platforms, on the other hand, cannot serve as a replacement for going to the movies because they are merely another option. Despite the fact that the pandemic wreaked havoc on OTT platforms, it had no effect on people reading more books.

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